

Solvent Extraction and Fluorimetric Determination of Beryllium—A Back Extraction Method

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A method for the detection and determination of beryllium has been developed using *N-p*-chlorophenylbenzohydroxamic acid (*N-p*-Cl BHA) and morin as reagents. A yellow coloured beryllium *N-p*-Cl-BHA-morin complex obeys Beer's law in the range 0.1–10 ppm at the pH 8.0–8.5. The molar absorptivity is found to be $9.4 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 410 nm. Effect of pH, concentration of reagent and morin and interference of diverse ions is discussed.

HYDROXAMIC acids are versatile reagents and widely used in analytical chemistry¹⁻³. Gravimetric determination of beryllium with hydroxamic acid has been reported^{4,5}. Spectrophotometric methods for the determination of beryllium has also been explored with hydroxamic acid⁶, but no details are available. In the present communication, the extraction and spectrophotometric method including fluorimetric estimation for the determination of beryllium has been described.

Experimental

A VSU2-P (C.Z Jena) spectrophotometer was used for the photometric measurements. A Systronics 335 digital pH meter equipped with glass and calomel electrodes was used for the pH measurements.

Chloroform and ethanol were purified by the standard method⁷. A standard beryllium solution ($7.998 \times 10^{-4} M$) was prepared by dissolving the requisite amount of beryllium sulphate ($\text{BeSO}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$) in double-distilled water (500 ml) and standardised volumetrically⁸. *N-p*-Chlorophenylbenzohydroxamic acid (*N-p*-Cl-BHA) 0.3% (w/v) solutions of reagent in chloroform was prepared for extraction and spectrophotometric determination of beryllium. A 0.01% (w/v) solution of morin in ethanol was used for the development of colour in spectrophotometric and fluorimetric determination of beryllium. The buffer solutions (pH 8.0–8.5) were prepared as per NBS standards⁹.

Extraction and spectrophotometric determination: To an aliquote of standard beryllium ($7.998 \times 10^{-4} M$), 10 ml buffer solution (pH 8) was added and diluted to 15 ml, followed by the addition of reagent solution (5 ml). The contents were shaken vigorously for 15 min and the phases were allowed to separate. The chloroform extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and transferred. The extraction was repeated to ensure the complete

recovery of beryllium. The extracts and washing were collected and to it was added morin solution (1 ml), developing an intense yellow colour. The spectrum was scanned and the absorbance determined at 410 nm against reagent blank.

Back-extraction and fluorimetric determination: The extracted Be-*N-p*-Cl-BHA complex (15 ml) was back-extracted with 0.5 M HCl. The extraction was repeated twice and the aqueous layer transferred. Then 1.0 N NaOH (1 ml), 10% EDTA (0.5 ml), 1% slantite (1 ml) and finally the ethanolic solution of morin (1 ml) were added to it. It was diluted to 25 ml with distilled water. The fluorescence was measured using 365 and 525 nm, primary and secondary filters, respectively. The beryllium concentration was computed from the calibration curve which was prepared by directly taking standard beryllium¹⁰.

Results and Discussion

Extraction and spectrophotometric determination of beryllium: The *N-p*-chlorophenylbenzohydroxamic acid (*N-p*-Cl-BHA) is used for the extraction and spectrophotometric determination of beryllium. The addition of morin enhances the molar absorptivity and gives fluorescence. The Be-*N-p*-Cl-BHA-morin complex has a maximum absorbance at 410 nm, hence all the measurements are taken at 410 nm.

Effect of pH: The maximum extraction (100%) of beryllium is obtained at pH 8.0–8.5. Below and above this pH the extraction decreases considerably. These data are recorded in Table 1.

Beer's law: The Be-*N-p*-Cl-BHA-morin coloured system obey's Beer's law in the range 0.1–10 ppm of Be at 410 nm and molar absorptivity is found to be $9.4 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Reagent concentration: A (5 ml) of 0.3% (w/v) solutions of *N-p*-Cl-BHA is most adequate for the

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF pH ON THE EXTRACTION OF BERYLLIUM-*N-p*-Cl-BHA COMPLEX

pH	Beryllium = 1.15 ppm, $\lambda_{max} = 410$ nm											
	2.0	4.0	5.0	6.0	7.0	7.5	8.0	8.2	8.5	8.7	9.0	10.0
% Extraction	N	N	2	10	30	40	100	100	100	60	30	5
Distribution ratio	—	—	0.02	1.5	2.5	16	a	a	a	23	18	0.8

N = No extraction, a = Too high to measure.

complete extraction of Be. The excess reagent may be used without any difficulty but has no effect in the colour development.

Morin concentration : Addition of a 1 ml of 0.01% morin is sufficient to obtain maximum colour intensity. The addition of excess amount of morin increases the blank correction. Hence a 1 ml of 0.01% morin concentration is kept constant for the determination of Be.

Fluorimetric determination of beryllium :

The Be-*N-p*-Cl-BHA complex is back-extracted (before addition of morin) from 0.05 M HCl and fluorescence is measured after addition of morin.

Calibration curve : The calibration curve is prepared⁹ taking standard Be (0.05 ppm).

Beer's law : The system obey's Beer's law in the range 0–0.42 ppm of Be.

Morin concentration : The fluorescence can be obtained with 0.7 ml 0.01% morin solution but the addition of 1ml of 0.01% morin solution was found to be most adequate for the maximum fluorescence. The lower concentration of morin gives erroneous results, and with the higher concentration of morin the blank adjustment (to zero reading in the fluorometer) could not be made.

Interference of diverse ions : A 0.15 ppm of Be was determined in presence of several diverse ions first extracting with *N-p*-chlorophenylbenzohydroxamic acid and back-extraction as described earlier. The only metal ions which can be extracted at pH 8.0–8.5 are La, Mg and Hg alongwith Be, and interfere. These interferences can be removed by masking Mg^{2+} and La^{3+} with sodium oxalate and Hg^{2+} with thiocyanate. The ions (60 mg of each) like Ba^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Ga^{3+} , rare earths, Co^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Zr^{IV} , Nb^V , Mo^{VI} , Ta^V , Ti^{IV} , Sb^{III} , Bi^{III} , As^{III} do not interfere in the determination of Be.

The present method has the advantage over the direct beryllium-morin fluorimetric determination where Zn, Li, Ca etc. are seriously interfere. The data on the recovery of Be from the standard samples are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL DATA ON THE RECOVERY OF BERYLLIUM

Be taken ppm	Be found ppm	Standard deviation*
Spectrophotometric method ($\lambda_{max} = 410$ nm)		
1.0	0.99	±0.01
1.5	1.51	±0.02
2.0	2.01	±0.02
2.5	2.48	±0.02
5.0	5.00	±0.01
7.5	7.49	±0.01
9.0	9.01	±0.02
Fluorimetric method		
0.100	0.100	±0.001
0.150	0.150	±0.001
0.200	0.210	±0.002
0.250	0.248	±0.003
0.300	0.299	±0.003
0.400	0.401	±0.001

* 7 determinations

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